

Extractive spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(V) using 3-hydroxy-2-(4-methoxyphenyl)-6-methyl-4H-chromen-4-one

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A simple, sensitive, rapid and selective method for the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(V) in trace amounts is proposed, using 3-hydroxy-2-(4-methoxyphenyl)-6-methyl-4H-chromen-4-one (HL) as a complexing agent and extracting the coloured 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) complex into 1,2-dichloroethane from 0.1 M CH₃COOH solution. It obeys Beer's law in the concentration range 0.23–2.45 μg ml⁻¹ V^V having molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of 2.54 × 10⁴ dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.00198 μg cm⁻² at 400 nm. The method has been applied satisfactorily to the analysis of various synthetic and technical samples.

Earlier used methods¹ for spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(V) suffer from interference from a large number of foreign ions, are time consuming and usually less sensitive ($\epsilon \sim 10^3$). Recently proposed methods² using different reagents also suffer from the same disadvantages though sensitivity is slightly improved in few cases^{3–5}. In the present communication, a new reagent 3-hydroxy-2-(4-methoxyphenyl)-6-methyl-4H-chromen-4-one (HL) has been proposed for the spectrophotometric determination of V^V with improved sensitivity and having advantages of high stability, selectivity and reproducibility.

Results and Discussion

Vanadium(V) formed an intense yellow complex with HL in acidic medium which was extractable into 1,2-dichloroethane. The complex had a maximum absorbance at 400 nm, where the reagent blank absorbed negligibly. The effect of different acids on the absorbance of vanadium(V) complex was studied at 0.12 M acidity and the absorbance decreased in the order : CH₃COOH > HCl > H₂SO₄ > H₃PO₄. Therefore, acetic acid medium was preferred for further studies.

It was found that for ≤ 25 μg V^V present in 10 ml aqueous phase, 0.07–0.14 M CH₃COOH, 0.8–1.3 ml 0.4% HL (in acetone) and 15–300 s shaking time with the solvent were optimum for transferring the complex quantitatively to the organic phase in a single extraction with an equal volume of 1,2-dichloroethane. The absorbance of the metal complex in different organic water immiscible solvents decreased in the order : 1,2-dichloroethane > chloroform > benzene > dichloromethane > diethyl ether > toluene > amyl acetate > isobutyl methyl ketone > butyl acetate > carbon tetrachloride > ethyl acetate. The complex was found stable

for 2 h in 1,2-dichloroethane.

Beer's law was obeyed over the concentration range of 0.23–2.45 μg ml⁻¹, as obtained from Ringbom curve at 400 nm. For nine replicate determinations of 1.0 μg ml⁻¹, the relative standard deviation was 0.008%. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the method were 2.54 × 10⁴ dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.00198 μg cm⁻² respectively. The composition of the complex, investigated by Job's method of continuous variations as modified by Vosburgh and Cooper⁶, showed that the metal ion and the ligand were present in the ratio 1 : 2 in the extracted species. This was further confirmed by the mole-ratio method.

Effect of diverse ions : The effect of various anions, complexing agents and cations (added in mg ml⁻¹ aqueous phase shown in parentheses) was studied by taking 1 μg

Table 1. Determination of V in synthetic and real samples

Sl. no.	Composition of sample (mg)	V added V found*	
		μg	μg
1.	Ag (0.1), U(0.05), Re(0.01), Se(1.0), Os(0.05)	25.0	25.0
2.	Th(0.05), U(0.01), Au(0.02), Ir(0.01), Nb(0.01)	5.0	4.9
3.	Ba(5.0), Be(3.0), Al(1.0), Ta(0.05), W(0.01) ^a	10.0	9.9
4.	Ni(0.3), Pt(0.01), Pd(0.01) ^b	5.0	5.0
5.	Co(0.104), Fe(0.068) ^c	28.0	28.0
6.	Fe(0.05), Co(0.01), Mn(0.01) ^c	5.0	5.04
7.	Reverberatory flue dust (100) ^d	5.0	5.1
8.	High speed steel super rapid extra 500(50) ^e	1% ^f	0.950%

*Average of duplicate analyses.

^aIn presence of 0.1 mg sodium citrate. ^bComposition analogous to palau.

^cCompositions analogous to vicalloy and permendur respectively; in presence of 0.2 mg sodium fluoride in each case. ^dIn presence of 40 mg thiourea and 0.2 mg sodium fluoride. ^eIn presence of 40 mg sulphite, 0.1 mg citrate and 0.2 mg fluoride as their sodium salts. ^fCertified value.

Table 2. Comparison of the present method with other methods

Sl. no.	Aqueous condition	Solvent/ λ_{\max} nm	Sandell's sensitivity, $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ / Molar absorptivity, $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$	Interfering metal ions
1.	V ^V , acidic medium, benzohydroxamic acid ^a	1-Hexanol, 450	0.012, 4.24×10^3	Fe ^{III} , Bi ^{III} , Sb ^{III} , Al ^{III} , Sn ^{II} , Ti ^{IV} , Zr ^{IV} , Mo ^{VI} , W ^{VI}
2.	V ^V , pH 3.5–4.5, picolinealdehyde benzothiazolylylhydrazone, shaking time 10 min ^b	Benzene, 528	0.0033, 1.54×10^4	Fe ^{III,II} , Co ^{II} , Pd ^{II}
3.	V ^V , CH ₃ COOH, sodium dithionite, 3-hydroxyflavone, colour development time 10 min ^c	1,2-Dichloroethane, 398–404	0.0014, 3.56×10^4	Ti ^{IV} , Al ^{III}
4.	V ^V , 0.7 M HCl, sodium sulphite, sodium acetate, 8-hydroxyquinoline ^d	Isobutyl methyl ketone, 430	0.0088, 5.73×10^3	Zr ^{IV} , Al ^{III} , Fe ^{III,II} , Co ^{II} , Cu ^{II}
5.	V ^V , HClO ₄ , persulphate, acetone, ammonium acetate, pH 3–3.5, 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol (PAN), waiting time 5 min ^e	Chloroform, 615	0.003, 1.69×10^4	Cu ^{II} , Fe ^{III} , Ni ^{II} , Cr ^{VI} , Co ^{II} , Bi ^{III} , U ^{VI}
6.	Present method	1,2-Dichloroethane, 400	0.00198, 2.54×10^4	Mo ^{VI} , Sn ^{II}

^aRef. 1. ^bRef. 3. ^cRef. 5. ^dRef. 9. ^eRef. 10.

ml⁻¹ of V in aqueous phase under the optimum conditions. Sulphate, bromide, chloride, iodide (10 each); sulphite, thiourea (4 each); phosphate (0.05); fluoride, tartrate (0.02 each) and citrate (0.01) when added before the addition of the reagent (HL), caused an error of <1%. Ascorbic acid, oxalate and disodium EDTA (0.1 each) interfered seriously. Zn^{II}, Co^{II}, Mn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Ba^{II}, Sr^{II} (1 each); Al^{III}, Be^{II} (0.5 each); Pb^{II}, Ni^{II} (0.4 each); Se^{IV} (0.2); Bi^{III} (0.18); U^{VI}, Os^{VIII}, Re^{VII}, Sb^{III}, Ag^I (0.01 each); Nb^V (0.009); Ta^V (0.008); Th^{IV}, Au^{III}, Ti^{IV}, Ir^{III}, Ru^{III} (0.005 each); Ce^{IV}, Pt^{IV}, Pd^{II} (0.001 each) did not affect the absorbance of the complex. Cu^{II} (0.12), W^{VI} (0.003) and Cr^{VI} (0.07) did not interfere in presence of thiourea (4), sodium citrate (0.01) and sodium sulphite (4) respectively. Similarly, Fe^{III} (0.007) and Zr^{IV} (0.002) were without effect in presence of sodium fluoride (0.02) in each case. Mo^{VI} and Sn^{II} even in traces interfered seriously.

Applications : The usefulness and applicability of the proposed method to synthetic and technical samples especially steel and flue dust (Table 1) were shown by satisfactory results. The proposed method had a better sensitivity than most of the reported spectrophotometric methods for vanadium(V) (Table 2). It also had a better freedom from disturbances from several important and frequently interfering elements in amounts ranging from equimolar to 1000-fold excess. The method was found simple and took only 5–6 min for a single determination.

Experimental

A Hitachi U-2000 spectrophotometer with 100 mm matched quartz cells was used. Solutions of V^V and other ions were prepared as reported earlier⁷. 3-Hydroxy-2-(4-methoxyphenyl)-6-methyl-4H-chromen-4-one (HL) (m.p. 190–192°) was synthesized⁸ and dissolved in acetone to give 0.4% (w/v) solution. Acetic acid solution (1 M) was prepared. 1,2-Dichloroethane (Qualigens SQ) was distilled and the b.p. 82.5–84.0° fraction was used.

High-speed steel super rapid extra 500 sample (0.05 g) was brought into solution (100 ml) as reported⁷ and vanadium determined in an aliquot (1 ml) of this solution after adding sodium sulphite (40 mg), sodium citrate (0.1 mg) and sodium fluoride (0.2 mg) before adding the reagent (HL). Reverberatory flue dust sample (0.1 g) obtained from copper manufacturing unit, was mixed with a solution of known vanadium content (1 mg) and brought into solution (100 ml) as reported⁷. Aliquots (0.5 ml) were analysed for vanadium by the proposed method after adding thiourea (40 mg) and sodium fluoride (0.2 mg) in each case.

Procedure : To a sample solution containing $\leq 25 \mu\text{g}$ of vanadium(V) and other ions were added 1 M CH₃COOH and 0.4% HL (1 ml each) and the volume was made up to 10 ml with deionized water. The contents were mixed gently and equilibrated once with an equal volume (10 ml) of 1,2-dichloroethane for 30 s. The organic phase was filtered

Note

to remove water droplets. The absorbance of the yellow complex was then measured at 400 nm against a reagent blank and the concentration of the metal ion was computed from a calibration curve prepared under identical conditions.

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